

Spectral and catalytic hydrogenation studies of Ru^{II} organometallics containing substituted tertiary phosphines

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Abstract : The reaction of [RuCl₂(COD)₂] with acetylacetone (acac)/Na₂CO₃ in the presence of dimethylformamide produces the precursor, [Ru(acac)₂(COD)]. Using this precursor two series of organometallics were prepared by adopting different experimental conditions. The first series of Ru^{II} organometallics with the formula [Ru(acac)₂L₂] were derived by treating [Ru(acac)₂COD] with tertiary phosphines and the second series of Ru^{II} organometallics with the formula [Ru(acac)₂(CO)L] were derived by treating [Ru(acac)₂COD] on bubbling of carbonmonoxide in the presence of the tertiary phosphines, where L = (2-formylphenyl)diphenylphosphine, (2-carboxyphenyl)diphenylphosphine, (3-carboxyphenyl)diphenylphosphine, (4-carboxyphenyl)diphenylphosphine, (carboxymethyl)diphenylphosphine, (2-pyridyl)diphenylphosphine. All these compounds are air stable. The tentative geometries of all the organometallics have been established on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H, ¹³C, ³¹P NMR and electronic spectral data. These organometallics were used as act catalysts and found to be efficient in hydrogenation of nitrobenzene/*o*-chloronitrobenzene/*m*-chloronitrobenzene/*o*-nitrotoluene/*m*-nitrotoluene to aniline/*o*-chloroaniline/*m*-chloroaniline/*o*-toluidine/*m*-toluidine, which were estimated spectrophotometrically.

Keywords : Organometallics, catalytic hydrogenation, acetylacetone, tertiary phosphines, ruthenium(II).

Ruthenium organometallics containing phosphorus ligands are currently of considerable interest due to their coordinating nature^{1,2} and catalytic activity³⁻⁵. Literature data reveals that the Ru^{II} phosphine compounds are effective homogeneous catalysts for hydrodegeneration reactions⁶⁻⁸. The majorities of the reported ruthenium catalysts are not stable in solution and may under go facile ligand dissociation and geometric isomerization. Further these catalytic systems are not soluble in water and may not be much useful in the utilization of industrial catalytic processes. In order to improve the solubility of the ruthenium phosphine compounds in polar solvents like water, ethanol, it is planned to introduce the carboxylated polar groups on to the phenyl rings of the phosphine and synthesized twelve carboxylated tertiary aryl phosphines. These complexes were utilized in the catalytic hydrogenation of nitrobenzene/*o*-chloronitrobenzene/*m*-chloronitrobenzene/*o*-nitrotoluene/*m*-nitrotoluene to aniline/*o*-chloroaniline/*m*-chloroaniline/*o*-toluidine/*m*-toluidine⁹, which were estimated spectrophotometrically using nitrous acid and *b*-naphthol¹⁰.

Results and discussion

The molecular formulae for all the organometallics were proposed by the assumption that ruthenium combines

with phosphine ligands in 1 : 2 molar ratio for 1-6 and 1 : 1 for 7-12 organometallics. The physical and analytical data is in good agreement with the proposed molecular formulae (Table 1).

All the Ru^{II} organometallics showed a characteristic peak between 1600 and 1500 cm⁻¹ and these values are assigned to the ketonic group¹¹. The infrared spectra have bands in the range 1590-1560 and 1515-1560 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to the combination of $\nu(\text{C-C}) + \nu(\text{C-O})$ and $\nu(\text{C-O}) + \nu(\text{C-C})$, respectively of a chelated *O*-bonded acetyl acetone moiety^{12,13}. The strong sharp band exhibited by the organometallics 7-12 in the range of 1920-1950 cm⁻¹ is attributed to $\nu(\text{CO})$ bonded to Ru^{II} metal centre¹⁴. The organometallics 1 and 7 exhibit a band corresponding to $\nu(\text{CHO})$ of tertiary phosphine in the range around 1610 cm⁻¹ and the organometallics 2-5, 8-11 possess a strong band in the range of 1715-1725 cm⁻¹ are ascribed to $\nu(\text{COOH})$ of phosphine. These two functional groups almost unchanged in the IR spectra of organometallics when compared to the free tertiary phosphine ligands which confirm the non-involvement of these functional groups in coordination with ruthenium metal centre¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Further, no change in the absorption

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of Ru^{II} organometallics with tertiary phosphines

Complex no.	Ru ^{II} complex formed	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Color	Yield (% , g)	Analysis (%) :		
					Found (Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ CHO) ₂] C ₄₈ H ₄₄ O ₆ P ₂ Ru	215	Dark brown	0.322 (70)	64.59 (65.45)	4.82 (4.99)	-
2.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂] C ₄₈ H ₄₄ O ₈ P ₂ Ru	228	Brown	0.333 (70)	67.03 (68.00)	2.99 (3.09)	-
3.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-3-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂] C ₄₈ H ₄₄ O ₈ P ₂ Ru	222	Light brown	0.292 (72)	68.70 (68.12)	5.61 (5.72)	-
4.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-4-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂] C ₄₈ H ₄₄ O ₈ P ₂ Ru	239	Green	0.360 (73)	68.43 (68.12)	5.32 (5.62)	-
5.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-CH ₂ COOH) ₂] C ₃₈ H ₄₄ O ₈ P ₂ Ru	226	Light green	0.298 (72)	57.68 (57.68)	5.01 (5.04)	-
6.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₅ H ₄ N) ₂] C ₄₄ H ₄₂ O ₄ N ₂ P ₂ Ru	235	Light green	0.254 (68)	64.02 (64.01)	5.02 (5.09)	3.27 (3.34)
7.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ CHO)] C ₃₀ H ₃₁ O ₆ PRu	259	Grey	0.221 (70)	52.32 (53.72)	5.21 (5.48)	-
8.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)] C ₃₀ H ₃₁ O ₇ PRu	257	Grey	0.340 (71)	58.01 (58.15)	4.98 (5.01)	-
9.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-3-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)] C ₃₀ H ₃₁ O ₇ PRu	261	Light brown	0.335 (73)	57.75 (58.15)	4.75 (5.01)	-
10.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-4-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)] C ₃₀ H ₃₁ O ₇ PRu	242	Brown	0.331 (69)	57.85 (58.15)	4.92 (5.01)	-
11.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-CH ₂ COOH)] C ₂₅ H ₂₉ O ₇ PRu	236	Light green	0.289 (72)	51.85 (52.30)	4.89 (5.04)	-
12.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₅ H ₄ N)] C ₂₇ H ₃₀ O ₅ NPRu	213	Grey	0.330 (71)	53.25 (54.91)	5.89 (6.08)	2.25 (2.31)

band of ring nitrogen of pyridyl phosphine in its organometallics 6 and 12 reveals non-participation of pyridyl nitrogen¹⁸. The new strong absorption band was found in all the Ru^{II} organometallics in the far infrared region 514–540 cm⁻¹ and is ascribed to $\nu(\text{Ru-P})$ ¹⁹. This observation reveals that carboxy, formyl and pyridyl substituted tertiary phosphines are coordinated to Ru^{II} metal through phosphorous atom only.

The ¹H NMR spectra of all the organometallics show singlet signal in the range 2.10–2.55 ppm assigned to the methyl protons of the chelated acetylaceton²⁰ i.e. the two CH₃ protons are identical with O,O-bonded mode. Further, another proton signal observed around 5.12–5.52 ppm which corresponds to the =CH proton of acetylaceton reveals that acetylaceton is bonded to the Ru^{II} metal ion in the anionic form^{12,21}. The multiplet signals which appeared in all the organometallics in the range 6.8–8.4 ppm are attributed to aromatic protons of phenyl rings of tertiary phosphine. The doublet signal

observed in the upfield region of NMR spectra of organometallics 5 and 11 around 3.50–3.60 ppm is ascribed to methylene protons of (carboxymethyl)-diphenylphosphine ligand¹⁹. The ¹H NMR signal displayed by organometallics 1 and 7 in the down field region around 10.65–10.36 ppm was ascribed to formyl proton of tertiary phosphine and another signal observed in the same down field region for other organometallics (2–5 and 8–11) in the range of 11.15–12.75 ppm is attributed to the carboxylic proton of tertiary phosphine. Appearance of this down field signals in the respective organometallics indicates clearly the non-participation of these functional groups in the coordination^{15–17}.

The ¹³C NMR spectral signals of Ru^{II} organometallics containing substituted tertiary phosphines are assigned by the comparison with the spectra of corresponding free ligands. The peak positions were in good agreement with the data of established Ru^{II} organometallics²². The ¹³C signal observed in the upfield region for the

Table 2. ¹H NMR spectral data of Ru^{II} organometallics

Sl. no.	Complex	¹ H peaks position (ppm)			
		Acetyl acetone (acac)		Tertiary phosphines	
		CH ₃ (s)	=CH (s)	Aryl (m)	-COOH (br)
1.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ CHO) ₂]	2.55	5.52	7.1–8.5	10.36 ^a
2.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂]	2.20	5.23	7.2–8.3	12.01
3.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-3-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂]	2.18	5.12	6.8–8.3	11.75
4.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-4-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂]	2.28	5.14	7.3–8.3	11.14
5.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-CH ₂ COOH) ₂]	2.12	5.13	7.2–8.5	11.13
				3.50 (δ) ^b	
6.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₅ H ₄ N) ₂]	2.15	5.32	7.0–8.2	–
7.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ CHO)]	2.43	5.52	7.1–8.06	10.65 ^a
8.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)]	2.1	5.13	7.4–8.12	12.01
9.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-3-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)]	2.2	5.25	6.9–8.08	11.95
10.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-4-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)]	2.15	5.34	7.2–8.40	11.25
11.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-CH ₂ COOH)]	2.2	5.25	7.2–8.30	12.30
				3.80 (δ) ^b	
12.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₅ H ₄ N)]	2.25	5.23	7.1–8.12	–

^a-CHO, ^b-CH₂-COOH.

organometallics in the range 22.80–24.56 ppm is assigned to methyl carbons of acetylacetone. The signal corresponding to the =CH carbon was detected in the downfield in the range of 109.23–106.32 ppm for all the organometallics. The carbonyl carbon of ketone in organometallics displayed signal in the range 191.25–

195.21 ppm. This clearly indicates the bonding of ketonic oxygen atoms of acetyl acetone to the metal ion^{12,15,19}. The aryl carbons of tertiary phosphines were resonated in the range of 128–138 ppm. Further, the methylene carbons of (carboxyphenyl)diphenylphosphine organometallics 5 and 11 exhibit a signal around 38.42–

Table 3. ¹³C and ³¹P NMR spectral data of Ru^{II} organometallics

Sl. no.	Complex	¹³ C peaks position (ppm)						³¹ P Peak position (ppm) (δ)
		acac				Tertiary phosphines		
		CO	CH ₃	-HC=	C=O	Aryl (m)	-COOH (br)	
1.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ CHO) ₂]		24.30	109.23	195.21	128.00–136.45	183.12 ^a	37.79; 48.68
2.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂]		22.80	107.94	193.24	132.00–134.00	172.28	39.45; 43.15
3.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-3-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂]		23.76	106.32	193.25	128.70–136.30	169.00	32.12; 45.30
4.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-4-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂]		23.52	107.43	191.34	134.00–136.00	172.34	42.58; 46.78
5.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-CH ₂ COOH) ₂]		24.56	108.01	192.34	136.00–138.00	174.10	37.29; 48.34
					34.43 ^b			
6.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₅ H ₄ N) ₂]		22.21	106.73	194.32	132.45–138.00	–	39.53; 48.42
7.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ CHO)]	217.01	24.30	109.01	195.21	128–136	183 ^a	32.03
8.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)]	214.02	22.40	107.87	192.31	130–134	172	31.75
9.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-3-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)]	216.04	22.80	107.78	191.26	132–134	173	31.72
10.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-4-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)]	214.03	23.52	106.32	194.3	137–132	169	31.05
11.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-CH ₂ COOH)]	215.38	22.80	107.68	192.10	138–134	170	32.5
						38.42 ^b		
12.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₅ H ₄ N)]	213.10	23.21	106.92	191.25	138–132	–	30.75

^a-CHO, ^b-CH₂-COOH.

Reduction of aromatic nitro groups to aromatic primary amino groups is further confirmed by NMR spectral analysis. The NMR spectra of nitro compounds do not show a peak at δ 4.13, whereas their hydrogenated products show one additional broad peak at δ 4.10 confirming the presence of aromatic primary amino groups in them.

The red colored azo dyes are formed with amino compounds by the diazotization with nitrous acid and coupling with β -naphthol¹⁰ (Scheme 2).

The percent yields of aniline/*o*-chloroaniline/*m*-chloroaniline/*o*-toluidine/*m*-toluidine with all the twelve ruthenium catalysts were estimated spectrophotometrically and are given in Table 4.

Experimental

Elemental data was obtained from Technical University of Berlin, Berlin, Germany by using a Perkin-Elmer 240C CHN elemental analyzer. UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu MPS-5000 spectrophotometer, IR spectra in KBr pellets on Nicolet 740 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra on Bruker WH 270 (270 MHz) using CDCl₃/DMSO solvent, ¹³C NMR on Bruker WH 270 (67.93 MHz), ³¹P NMR on WH 270 (109.29 MHz). The hydrogenation unit consists of three necked double walled glass drain which in turn is connected to a double walled hydrogen burette through which water at the desired temperature from a thermostat is circulated.

AnalaR grade reagents, freshly distilled solvents and pure and dry hydrogen gas were used throughout the investigations. The precursor, [Ru(acac)₂(COD)] was

Scheme 2. Colored products formed between amino derivatives and β -naphthol.

prepared²⁸ by heating [Ru(COD)Cl₂], which is commercially available (Aldrich Chemical Company, Inc., FRG) with acetylacetonone and anhydrous Na₂CO₃ in the presence of DMF. All the formyl, carboxyl and pyridyl tertiary aryl phosphine ligands were prepared as per the literature procedures^{28,15-17}.

Table 4. Percent yields of amino derivatives formed by using Ru^{II} organometallic catalysts

Sl. no.	Complex	Aniline yield (%)	<i>o</i> -Chloro-aniline yield (%)	<i>m</i> -Chloro-aniline yield (%)	<i>o</i> -Toluidine yield (%)	<i>m</i> -Toluidine yield (%)
1.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ CHO) ₂]	83.27	85.23	79.43	89.15	78.76
2.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂]	77.58	69.99	73.02	78.22	71.98
3.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-3-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂]	90.29	88.23	89.79	86.98	88.97
4.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-4-C ₆ H ₄ COOH) ₂]	76.66	75.03	72.98	77.12	76.06
5.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-CH ₂ COOH) ₂]	75.03	71.76	74.34	76.02	72.83
6.	[Ru(acac) ₂ (Ph ₂ P-2-C ₅ H ₄ N) ₂]	92.88	90.76	89.45	89.61	91.23
7.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ CHO)]	81.82	81.15	79.54	78.74	80.23
8.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)]	76.54	74.43	75.87	77.65	76.23
9.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-3-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)]	69.65	70.24	69.56	71.54	70.21
10.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-4-C ₆ H ₄ COOH)]	78.54	76.48	79.76	74.27	76.58
11.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-CH ₂ COOH)]	81.90	79.54	80.58	78.65	78.21
12.	[Ru(acac) ₂ CO(Ph ₂ P-2-C ₅ H ₄ N)]	80.85	79.23	81.54	78.36	79.54

Synthesis of Ru^{II} organometallics of the type [Ru(acac)₂L₂] (OMC.1-6) :

[Ru(acac)₂(COD)] (0.5 mmol) was dissolved in 10 ml of acetone in a schlenk flask. To this solution, a solution of (2-formylphenyl)diphenylphosphine (1 mmol) in 10 ml of acetone was added and mixture was refluxed for 1 h. The product formed in the solution was collected by filtration, washed with diethylether and vacuum dried. The compound was recrystallized using dichloromethane and diethylether solvent mixture. The procedure is repeated by changing other five substituted phosphines one after the other.

Synthesis of Ru^{II} organometallics of the type [Ru(acac)₂(CO)(L)] (OMC.7-12) :

In a 100 ml schlenk flask having magnetic stirrers, a 10 ml solution of [Ru(acac)₂(COD)] (0.5 mmol) in acetone and 10 ml solution of (2-formylphenyl)diphenylphosphine (0.5 mmol) in acetone were taken. The resultant mixture was refluxed under heat for a period of 30 min during which CO gas was bubbled through the solution to get a grey colored compound and then cooled to room temperature. The compound was filtered, washed with diethylether and dried *in vacuo*. The product was recrystallized using dichloromethane and diethylether solvent mixture. The procedure is repeated by changing other five substituted phosphines one after the other.

Catalytic hydrogenation :

The DMF solution is saturated with hydrogen and then a 0.01 mmol of catalyst (Catalyst-1) was added. The catalyst goes in to the solution in few min. The reaction system was evacuated and flushed with hydrogen for few min and a 0.01 mmol of nitrobenzene/*o*-chloronitrobenzene/*m*-chloronitrobenzene/*o*-nitrotoluene/*m*-nitrotoluene in DMF was injected. The hydrogen absorption begins as soon as the shaking is started. The process was continued for 1 h. The resulting mixture was cooled and extracted with chloroform, the organic layer was separated, washed with water and dried over magnesium sulphate and evaporated to give the aniline/*o*-chloroaniline/*m*-chloroaniline/*o*-toluidine/*m*-toluidine. The products formed were estimated spectrophotometrically by diazocoupling reaction using nitrous acid and β-naphthol. The procedure is repeated by changing ruthenium catalyst.

Conclusion :

A facile synthetic route to Ru^{II} organometallics containing substituted tertiary phosphines has been described. Based on the spectral data, it is confirmed that

the Ru^{II} metal is coordinated to two molecules of acetylacetonate in the O,O-bonded mode and two molecules of tertiary phosphine ligands in the organometallics (1-6) with *cis* configuration. In the case of organometallics (7-12) two acetyl acetone molecules in the O,O-bonded mode, one tertiary phosphine ligand and one carbon monoxide are coordinated to Ru^{II} metal. Octahedral geometry is tentatively proposed for all the Ru^{II} organometallics. These organometallics are found to be efficient in the catalytic hydrogenation reactions.

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